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**Effects of raw and roasted high oleic soybeans on milk production
of high-producing dairy cows**

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INTERPRETATIVE SUMMARY

Effects of raw and roasted high oleic soybeans on milk production of high-producing dairy cows. *By Bales et al., page XXX.* The objective of our study was to determine the effects of roasted versus raw high *cis*-9 C18:1 soybeans on milk production responses of high-producing dairy cows. Overall inclusion of high *cis*-9 C18:1 soybeans, regardless of roasted or raw, increased dry matter intakes and the yields of milk, 3.5% FCM, ECM, milk fat, milk protein, milk lactose, and preformed milk fatty acids but decreased urea nitrogen in milk and blood compared to a control treatment. Roasted high *cis*-9 C18:1 soybeans did not affect dry matter intake but increased the yields of milk, 3.5% FCM, ECM, milk fat, milk protein, milk lactose, and preformed milk fatty acids and decreased urea nitrogen in milk and blood compared to treatments containing raw *cis*-9 C18:1 soybeans. The addition of a rumen by-pass protein supplement to raw *cis*-9 C18:1 soybeans increased milk protein and decreased urea nitrogen in milk and blood compared to a treatment of only raw *cis*-9 C18:1 soybeans.

Supplemental Table S1. Protein supply predictions from NASEM (2021) model¹

Variable	Treatment ²			
	CON	RST	RAW-D	RAW-U
RUP, %CP ^{3,4}	35.4	45.2	34.6	39.9
RDP, %CP ⁵	64.6	54.8	65.4	60.1
Ruminal Digestion and Outflow				
RDP – Microbial Protein Balance, g/d	1285	927	1343	1042
RUP, g/d	1547	2082	1510	1846
Metabolizable Protein Supply, g/d	2785	3121	2776	3030
MP from Microbes, kg/d	1520	1406	1547	1479
MP from RUP, kg/d	1270	1715	1234	1551
Dietary MP Supply, g/d	2784	3121	2777	3029
Predicted Supply, g/d				
Lysine	209	227	209	223
Methionine	58	61	58	60
Predicted Metabolizable AA Efficiency				
Lysine	0.75	0.72	0.78	0.74
Methionine	0.88	0.88	0.91	0.89
EAA	1381	1530	1379	1492
Other AA	2472	2786	2464	2698

¹Estimated predictions based on NASEM (2021) software using data from Table 1 and Table 2 in current study to reflect cow performance during the experiment.

²CON = no HOSB supplementation; RST = 16% DM roasted and ground HOSB; RAW-D = 16% DM raw and ground HOSB; RAW-U = 16% DM raw and ground HOSB + by-pass protein.

³Adapted from diet summary report from NASEM (2021) model output using equation: $([RUP, \%DM]/[CP, \%DM]) \times 100$.

⁴The RUP content of roasted soybeans was changed within the NASEM (2021) model utilizing values from Lin and Kung, 1999.

⁵Adapted from diet summary report from NASEM (2021) model output using equation: $([RDP, \%DM]/[CP, \%DM]) \times 100$.

Supplemental Table S2. Milk production responses by week of period for cows fed treatment diets (n=36)¹

Variable	Week (W)	Treatment ²				SEM ³	P-value ⁴		Contrast	
		CON	RST	RAW-D	RAW-U		Trt x Week	CON vs HOSOY	RST vs RAW	PRTN
Milk Yield, kg/d	W1	44.9	46.3	43.6	44.3	1.26	0.01	0.85	<0.01	0.35
	W2	42.6	47.0	42.5	44.8			<0.01	<0.001	<0.01
	W3	41.7	46.5	42.5	42.9			<0.01	<0.001	0.63
	W4	41.7	44.6	40.6	43.0			0.10	<0.01	<0.01
	W5	40.5	45.0	42.2	43.5			<0.001	<0.01	0.08
ECM Yield, kg/d ⁵	W1	46.3	50.1	47.0	47.1	1.18	0.01	0.01	<0.001	0.86
	W2	44.0	50.7	46.1	47.6			<0.001	<0.001	0.09
	W3	43.8	50.0	45.9	45.7			<0.001	<0.001	0.84
	W4	43.8	47.1	43.5	45.3			0.03	<0.01	0.03
	W5	42.4	47.4	45.5	46.2			<0.001	0.03	0.40
3.5% FCM Yield, kg/d ⁶	W1	45.7	50.3	47.4	47.2	1.21	0.01	<0.01	<0.001	0.87
	W2	43.7	51.1	46.5	47.8			<0.001	<0.001	0.14
	W3	43.4	50.4	46.1	46.0			<0.001	<0.001	0.84
	W4	43.4	47.5	43.7	45.5			<0.01	<0.001	0.04
	W5	42.0	47.9	45.7	46.3			<0.001	0.01	0.46
Milk Fat Yield, kg/d	W1	1.62	1.87	1.77	1.73	0.05	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	0.23
	W2	1.56	1.90	1.74	1.75			<0.001	<0.001	0.76
	W3	1.56	1.87	1.71	1.67			<0.001	<0.001	0.28
	W4	1.56	1.74	1.62	1.68			<0.001	0.01	0.08
	W5	1.52	1.75	1.69	1.68			<0.001	0.03	0.65
Milk Fat Content, %	W1	3.66	4.14	4.02	4.02	0.07	0.05	<0.001	0.02	0.92
	W2	3.77	4.08	4.10	3.94			<0.001	0.16	<0.01
	W3	3.77	4.10	4.05	3.95			<0.001	0.03	0.05
	W4	3.73	3.92	4.03	3.95			<0.001	0.12	0.10
	W5	3.73	3.91	4.06	3.88			<0.001	0.14	<0.01
Milk Protein Yield, kg/d	W1	1.49	1.52	1.41	1.43	0.04	<0.01	0.13	<0.001	0.45
	W2	1.39	1.51	1.38	1.44			0.03	<0.001	0.02
	W3	1.39	1.48	1.38	1.37			0.26	<0.001	0.74
	W4	1.39	1.41	1.31	1.39			0.24	0.01	<0.01

	W5	1.34	1.41	1.38	1.40			0.01	0.31	0.32
Milk Protein Content, %	W1	3.32	3.32	3.24	3.25			<0.01	<0.001	0.52
	W2	3.29	3.22	3.25	3.23			<0.01	0.21	0.27
	W3	3.34	3.20	3.25	3.20	0.04	<0.001	<0.001	0.20	0.02
	W4	3.37	3.18	3.25	3.24			<0.001	<0.001	0.47
	W5	3.37	3.15	3.29	3.24			<0.001	<0.001	0.04
Milk Lactose Yield, kg/d	W1	2.19	2.27	2.14	2.17			0.85	<0.01	0.34
	W2	2.07	2.32	2.10	2.20			<0.001	<0.001	0.01
	W3	2.02	2.28	2.08	2.11	0.07	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.53
	W4	2.03	2.21	2.00	2.12			0.02	<0.001	<0.01
	W5	1.96	2.21	2.07	2.13			<0.001	<0.01	0.09
Milk Lactose Content, %	W1	4.88	4.90	4.89	4.91			<0.01	0.98	0.07
	W2	4.85	4.93	4.94	4.92			<0.001	0.98	0.10
	W3	4.84	4.90	4.90	4.91	0.02	<0.01	<0.001	0.67	0.13
	W4	4.86	4.94	4.93	4.92			<0.001	0.15	0.56
	W5	4.85	4.92	4.91	4.91			<0.001	0.41	0.65
MUN, ug/mL	W1	12.6	10.3	12.1	11.2			<0.001	<0.001	<0.01
	W2	12.8	10.9	11.8	11.2			<0.001	0.01	0.04
	W3	13.4	11.2	11.4	11.8	0.23	<0.01	<0.001	0.07	0.18
	W4	12.3	9.86	10.8	10.2			<0.001	0.01	0.02
	W5	13.1	10.3	11.5	10.9			<0.001	<0.01	0.05

¹Experimental diets fed to 36 cows in replicated 4 × 2 truncated Latin squares with 35-d periods and balanced for carryover effects. Samples and data for production variables collected during the last 5 d of each treatment period (d 30 to 35).

²CON = no HOSB supplementation; RST = 16% DM roasted and ground HOSB; RAW-D = 16% DM raw and ground HOSB; RAW-U = 16% DM raw and ground HOSB + by-pass protein

³Greatest SEM.

⁴Contrasts are: CON vs HOSOY = CON vs 1/3 (RST + RAW-D + RAW-U); RST vs RAW = RST vs 1/2 (RAW-D + RAW-U); PRTN = RAW-D vs RAW-U.

⁵Fat-corrected milk; 3.5 % FCM = [(0.4324 × kg milk) + (16.216 × kg milk fat)] (NRC, 2001).

⁶Energy-corrected milk; ECM = [(0.327 × kg milk) + (12.95 × kg milk fat) + (7.20 × kg milk protein)] (DRMS, 2014). This equation corrects milk to a 0.68 Mcal/kg energy basis.

Supplemental Table S3. Milk fatty acid content for cows fed treatment diets (n=36)¹

Variable	Treatment ²				SEM ³	Contrast ⁴		
	CON	RST	RAW-D	RAW-U		CON vs HOSOY	RST vs RAW	PRTN
Summation by source, g/100 g								
de novo	28.5	24.7	25.3	24.9	0.31	<0.001	0.16	0.20
Mixed	39.5	28.1	29.6	29.1	0.45	<0.001	<0.01	0.25
Preformed	31.6	47.4	45.6	45.9	0.46	<0.001	<0.001	0.38
Selected individual fatty acids ⁵ , g/100 g								
C4:0	2.65	2.86	2.74	2.79	0.05	<0.01	0.02	0.30
C6:0	1.99	2.01	1.97	2.00	0.03	0.79	0.20	0.27
C8:0	1.26	1.22	1.21	1.20	0.02	0.01	0.45	0.73
C10:0	3.71	3.11	3.26	3.17	0.07	<0.001	0.08	0.19
C12:0	4.75	3.53	3.81	3.67	0.09	<0.001	0.01	0.1
C14:0	12.9	11.1	11.5	11.2	0.14	<0.001	0.14	0.16
C16:0	37.5	26.9	28.2	27.8	0.44	<0.001	<0.01	0.25
<i>cis</i> -9 C16:1	1.97	1.25	1.27	1.27	0.04	<0.001	0.46	0.79
C18:0	6.54	10.7	11.6	11.9	0.26	<0.001	<0.001	0.28
<i>trans</i> -6 to -8 C18:1	0.20	0.48	0.35	0.36	0.01	<0.001	<0.001	0.26
<i>trans</i> -9 C18:1	0.16	0.30	0.23	0.23	0.01	<0.001	<0.001	0.67
<i>trans</i> -10 C18:1	0.44	0.54	0.37	0.36	0.03	0.41	<0.001	0.76
<i>trans</i> -11 C18:1	0.52	0.76	0.42	0.44	0.03	0.63	<0.001	0.61
<i>trans</i> -12 C18:2	0.32	0.47	0.34	0.35	0.01	<0.001	<0.001	0.70
<i>cis</i> -9 C18:1	15.4	27.0	25.2	25.5	0.30	<0.001	<0.001	0.31
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12 C18:2	2.27	2.01	1.71	1.76	0.04	<0.001	<0.001	0.26
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12, <i>cis</i> -15 C18:3	0.42	0.45	0.39	0.41	0.01	0.83	<0.001	0.04

¹Experimental diets fed to 36 cows in replicated 4 × 2 truncated Latin squares with 35-d periods and balanced for carryover effects. Samples and data for production variables collected during the last 5 d of each treatment period (d 30 to 35). ²CON = no HOSB supplementation; RST = 16% DM roasted and ground HOSB; RAW-D = 16% DM raw and ground HOSB; RAW-U = 16% DM raw and ground HOSB + by-pass protein. ³Greatest SEM. ⁴Contrasts are: CON vs HOSOY = CON vs 1/3 (RST + RAW-D + RAW-U); RST vs RAW = RST vs 1/2 (RAW-D + RAW-U); PRTN = RAW-D vs RAW-U. ⁵A total of approximately 80 individual fatty acids were quantified. Only select fatty acids are reported in the table.